

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF ALUMINIUM WITH MANDELIC ACID

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From pH and conductance measurements it is concluded that mandelic acid is a good chelating agent for aluminium. Three chelates corresponding to 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 formulae are formed. The chelate of composition 1:1 is formed at a lower pH value, while 1:2 and 1:3 chelates, which occur at pH 6.5 and 7.8 respectively, are more stable than 1:1 chelate. The chelation takes place easily on account of the close proximity of the acidic and electron-donating groups, a fact which is essential for formation of the ring containing the metal atom.

There are many references in literature of complexes of aluminium with aliphatic as well as aromatic hydroxy-acids. Aluminium chelates with salicylic acid were first studied by Burrows and Wark (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 455). A detailed study of these complexes was carried out by Babko *et al.* (*J. Gen. Chem., U.S.S.R.*, 1948, 18, 1617). But studies on complexes of aluminium with mandelic acid are lacking. This work concerns the present study.

EXPERIMENTAL

First a solution of aluminium chloride (A.R., B.D.H.) of approximate strength was prepared. Its aluminium content was estimated gravimetrically by precipitating aluminium as aluminium oxinate (Vogel, "Text-Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1951, p. 372). Mandelic acid used was of A.R. quality of B.D.H.

pH of the solution was determined by a Beckman pH meter, H₂ type, having a glass and a saturated calomel electrodes. The instrument was standardised with a standard buffer solution supplied by the manufacturers. Electrical conductivity was measured by Callen Kamp's Kohlrausch slide wire with an audio-frequency oscillator in the circuit, the null point being detected by means of a headphone.

In all the measurements monovariant method was adopted. To constant volumes of aluminium chloride varying amounts of chelating agent were added. Thus three sets of mixtures containing aluminium chloride and chelating agent in the ratio of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 were prepared. To these mixtures varying quantities of NaOH solution of known strength were added. The total volume in every case was kept constant. The solutions were left for about 24 hours to attain equilibrium. pH and specific conductance of the mixtures were determined at a constant temperature of 20.5°. For comparison, aluminium chloride and mandelic acid were titrated potentiometrically and conductometrically with a standard alkali solution under the same conditions.

Only the representative pH data for 1 : 1 mixture are shown in Table I, while others have been depicted in graphs (Figs. 1 and 2).

TABLE I

pH values of 1:1 mixture of aluminium chloride and mandelic acid at different concentrations containing different quantities of alkali.

Equiv. alkali added.	pH values at			Equiv. alkali added.	pH values at		
	M/250.	M/500.	M/1000.		M/250.	M/500.	M/1000.
0.0	3.00	3.05	3.10	2.8	5.70	5.90	6.00
0.2	3.05	3.10	3.15	3.0	5.80	6.10	6.20
0.4	3.10	3.17	3.20	3.4	6.20	6.50	6.80
0.8	3.30	3.37	3.40	3.8	6.70	7.10	7.30
1.2	3.55	3.60	3.70	4.2	7.70	8.20	8.30
1.6	3.87	3.98	4.35	4.6	9.30	10.80	10.90
2.0	5.15	5.30	5.50	5.0	10.60	11.40	11.45
2.4	5.40	5.55	5.70	5.4	11.00	11.50	11.55

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 represents the changes in the pH occurring when aluminium chloride, mandelic acid and their mixtures are titrated with alkali. Curve A (1:0) is for $M/250$ aluminium chloride solution alone; while curves B to D are for 1:1 to 1:3 mixtures. Curve E represents pH changes when only mandelic acid ($M/250$) is titrated against alkali.

FIG. 1

From curve A (Fig. 1) it is clear that precipitation of aluminium hydroxide starts at pH 5.2, when nearly three equivalents of alkali have been added. At pH 9.8, when nearly four equivalents of alkali have been added, the above precipitate dissolves to furnish sodium aluminate.

Curve E shows at once that there is a sudden rise in pH, when nearly one equivalent of alkali has been added. In case of curve B, which represents pH changes for 1:1 mixture, the pH value in the beginning, *i.e.*, when no alkali has been added, is 3.0, which is lower than that of aluminium chloride (3.78) and mandelic acid (5.1) solution alone. This is due to the complex formation as a result of which hydrogen of hydroxyl group of the acid becomes more labile and therefore lowers the pH value. This is further confirmed as there is an inflection at two equivalents of alkali, which indicates the formation of 1:1 chelate:

Further addition of alkali brings about a sudden increase in hydroxyl-ion concentration.

Curve C represents pH values of 1 : 2 mixture. As in the previous case, the pH to start with is less than 3.78. The curve has an inflection at about four equivalents of alkali which indicates that a 1:2 chelate is also formed. The reaction is represented as:

Here again due to liberation of four equivalents of H⁺ ions per g. ion of Al, the inflection occurs at four equivalents of alkali.

Curve D represents the pH values of 1 : 3 mixtures. There is only one well-defined inflection at six equivalents of alkali, which confirms the formation of 1:3 chelate according to the equation :

Similar curves were obtained for concentrations M/500 and M/1000 also.

Conductance Measurements

Fig. 2 represents the changes taking place in the specific conductance when different mixtures are titrated against a standard alkali. Here the abscissa represents the number of alkali equivalents

FIG. 2

added per g. ion of aluminium and ordinate represents sp. conductance. Curve A, which is for aluminium chloride solution alone, has two inflections at 3 and 4 equivalents of alkali, showing the precipitation of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ and formation of sodium aluminate. Curve B for 1 : 1 mixture has minimum specific conductivity at 2 equivalents of alkali which can be explained as follows.

Due to formation of 1:1 chelate, 2 equivalents of H^+ ions/g. ion of Al are set free. Therefore its specific conductance is greater than that of AlCl_3 solution in the beginning. On addition of sodium hydroxide, sp. conductance decreases as H^+ ions are removed. When all the H^+ ions are used up, the specific conductance increases because of excess of OH^- ions. Thus, the curve is actually analogous to the titration curve of strong acid and strong base. Therefore from the position of inflection at two equivalents of alkali, the formation of a 1 : 1 chelate is inferred.

Curve C representing the sp. conductance of 1 : 2 mixture, when titrated against alkali, has got one minimum at four equivalents of alkali. This minimum is attributed to 1 : 2 chelate and corresponds to equation (2). The increase in sp. conductance afterwards is due to excess of NaOH. Similarly in agreement with the theoretical expectation, curve D, which is for 1 : 3 mixtures, shows only one well-defined inflection at six equivalents of alkali required for 1 : 3 chelate. As the ratio of the chelating agent is increased, the curves, exhibiting higher complexes, do not denote lower ones as in the presence of excess of chelating ligand, these titrations can hardly show any indication of lower complexes.

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